
Research

Bangladesh-China Bilateral Trade Relations: An Analysis of Current Trends

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Abstract: Bangladesh-China relations have strengthened over recent decades due to financial, military, trade, and political ties. Relations between Bangladesh and China were originally established in 1976. Progressive leaders of the two countries have pledged to advance China-Bangladesh bilateral trade relations. The strengthening of China-Bangladesh relations and the promotion of trade relations and financial participation are the main interests of these two countries which help in the development of the people. Approved social events, correspondence, and concerted efforts and cooperation at the level of advanced government authorities were agreed upon. To develop Bangladesh-China bilateral trade relations, the administration empowered to redesign investments in the main assembly, the Joint Monetary and Exchange Board of Trustees, and the Joint Horticulture Council, including machinery and other Content. The various gatherings are trying to increase compensation, speculation, cultivation, transportation, and infrastructure development, depending on the basic bilateral trade between the two countries. The Belt and Road Initiative has contributed to the development of bilateral trade relations between the two countries. "Sister Cities" alliances have been established. This paper aims to analyze and explore current bilateral trade relations and trade agreements, investment, agriculture, transport, and infrastructure development. An exploration of bilateral relations between Bangladesh and China. This article attempts to reveal the current pattern of bilateral relations between Bangladesh and China. This research paper is based on a literature review and related data and analyzed in consultation with recent bilateral trade relations scholarship.

Keywords: Bangladesh-China bilateral trade relations, cultural exchange, geopolitical, economic, and diplomatic interests

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Introduction

Chinese President Xi Jinping and Premier Li Keqiang congratulated the President and Prime Minister of Bangladesh on the 51st anniversary of Bangladesh's independence on March 27, 2022. In 2021, Chinese President Xi Jinping sent a message of congratulations on the 50th anniversary of Bangladesh's independence and the glorious victory of the Bengali nation. Xi Jinping President of Bangladesh. In a letter to Abdul Hamid, our cooperation under the Belt and Road

Initiative has been progressing well in recent years, adding new impetus to our bilateral relations and becoming more helpful to the people of our two countries, which include the mutual desire for stronger relations in the current competitive economic era. The Chinese president said both countries were at an "important stage of revival and development" when China's "dream of great national renaissance" and Bangladesh's dream of "Golden Bangla" could well be linked. China's position towards Bangladesh has been focused on economics and trade for 51 years since 1971. From animosity to embrace and it is a "strategic partnership in bilateral trade between the two countries". Bangladesh and China have developed a deep economic interdependence that is increasingly leaning towards China. Leadership in the international arena means a restructuring of bilateral and multilateral relations in trade, economics, and other issues. Determining the national interest through. Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina has shown excellent leadership to move the country towards development while maintaining the international reputation of Bangladesh. Her leadership has influenced the bilateral trade relationship between China and Bangladesh based on mutual trust and interests. A great commitment between Bangladesh and China in 1976. A collective effort of cooperation and Diplomatic relations was established to leverage K. The progressive leaders of the two countries pledged to improve China-Bangladesh relations for national development. China-Bangladesh economic development and cooperation serve the interests of both countries, meet the goals of the people of the country, and play a supportive role in harmony and progress in the world. Therefore, the two countries have chosen to establish a "close partnership of cooperation" based on the values of essential benefits. Visits of the heads of state of the two countries and contacts between the two countries have agreed to promote cordial bilateral trade between government offices, parliaments, ideological groups, and military and legislative assemblies. Arrangements were made to advance correspondence and cooperation at the governmental level and to improve the instruments of development participation, including the Conciliation Conference, the Joint Economic and Trade Committee, and the Joint Agricultural Committee. The two countries are working in response to the perception of increasing exchange, estimation, agricultural trade, transportation, and cooperation based on equity and shared benefits framework, (Choudhury, 2010)(Islam, 2019). The methodology of this research paper is qualitative in analytical and descriptive nature. An approach followed, and necessary information was collected from research monographs, press releases, and electronic sources.

Methods of Bilateral Trade Relationship Analysis:

The present paper uses a panel data research method to analyze export-import along with the bilateral trade relationship between Bangladesh and China. To understand the status of export-import and trade balance during bilateral trade, simple statistics for the years 2010 to 2019 and 2020 to 2022 have been analyzed. The methodology of this paper is analytical and descriptive. The research followed a qualitative approach, with secondary data from various books, journal articles, and newspapers. The necessary information has been collected from periodicals, research monographs, press releases, and electronic sources. Diplomatic documents made between Bangladesh and China have also been used in this research paper. Researchers have also collected information from BBS, EPB, CPD, Bangladesh directories, banks, and other institutions. This research paper is written based on a literature review and related data and analyzed in consultation with recent bilateral trade relations scholarship.

Bangladesh-China Relations:

Both countries have emerged as reliable partners to extend China's economic, commercial, military, and diplomatic support to Bangladesh. The recent visit of the Chinese President to Bangladesh has made it the peak of Bangladesh-China bilateral relations. Now Bangladesh's relations are not only in bilateral relations but also in international politics, especially in geopolitics. Chinese President Xi Jinping cited the "strategic partnership" as a serious matter. China and Bangladesh established diplomatic relations on 4- October 1975. However, through the Bangladesh-Pakistan-India Agreement of 1974, China subsequently withdrew its opposition to UN recognition of Bangladesh's independence. After Mujib's assassination in 1975, China recognized Bangladesh. China and Bangladesh, close neighbors in the Asian region, have maintained deep political, economic, diplomatic, and military relations based on mutual trust and interests

since the establishment of their diplomatic relations in 1975(Ahmed, 2013). Diplomatic relations between the two countries were established on 04 October 1975, soon after China formally recognized Bangladesh on 10 August 1975,(Uddin, 2015). In 2002 Bangladesh's BNP-led four-party coalition government adopted a "Look East Policy" to maximize economic and strategic gains. Although this policy change was aimed at bilateral trade and multilateral relations, Bangladesh also wanted closer relations with China. Development of Chittagong Port China and Bangladesh signed a mutual agreement for joint economic development on equal terms. Therefore, according to researchers, China's Chittagong Port project in Bangladesh There is no military motive behind the funding, (Chittagong Port: Bangladesh's trump card in balancing diplomacy).

The economic and trade interests of the two countries have strengthened their bilateral trade relations. China-Bangladesh trade volume was only 3.06 million US dollars in the year of establishment of diplomatic relations, the rapid expansion of bilateral trade brought their trade volume to 12.40 billion US dollars in the 2017-2018 fiscal year (UNB, June 30, 2020) (FE Online Report, 16 March 2019). Bangladesh's proximity to the Bay of Bengal in the Indian Ocean, as well as Bangladesh's emergence as a coastal state, increase Bangladesh's geostrategic significance in the South Asian region, (Uddin, 2015). The historical development of Sino-Bangladesh relations under all the governments of Bangladesh during different regimes is described below.

Bangladesh-China relations during Ziaur Rahman's regime (1975-1981):

China-Bangladesh economic ties can be traced back to the military regime (1975-1981) led by former Bangladesh President General Ziaur Rahman. After coming to power in November 1975, Ziaur Rahman developed Bangladesh's active engagement with China(Sarker & Yesmin, 2020). During Ziaur Rahman's regime, Sino-Bangladesh economic relations began successfully and laid a solid foundation for bilateral relations. The two countries held the first formal bilateral contact on economic assistance in April 1976 (Quiyum & Jahirul, 2021). During Ziaur Rahman's visit to China as its Chief Executive and Chief of the Chief, the first high-level official visit from Bangladesh to China, several agreements such as economic and technical cooperation agreement and trade payment agreement were signed between the two countries. Both sides to increase the volume of bilateral trade. Agreed to exchange US\$14 million worth of goods by every possible means (Sarker, 2014). The then-Chinese Vice Premier Li Jianyan was invited to visit Bangladesh in March 1978 which initiated the development of Sino-Bangladesh bilateral relations. It marked the first visit of Chinese leadership to Bangladesh and inaugurated a five-year cooperation agreement in economy, science, and technology between the two countries (Amjad, Rehmani, & Mao). In August 1980, during another visit of Ziaur Rahman to China, the two governments also signed a loan agreement and an air transport agreement. China agreed to provide 45 million USD as development assistance to Bangladesh under that agreement(Hasan, 1979). In addition to economic assistance, Sino-Bangladesh bilateral relations in trade also improved during Zia's tenure. Since then, bilateral relations between the two countries have developed considerably, especially in the economic field.

Bangladesh-China relations during Hussain Mohammad Ershad's regime (1982-1990):

Sino-Bangladesh relations gained great importance during the authoritarian rule of Bangladesh from 1982 to 1990 under the then-president of Bangladesh, Lieutenant-General Hussain Mohammad Ershad. Ershad made the foundation of Sino-Bangladesh relations strong and building relations with China a top priority(Chowdhury, 2013). Since coming to power in a military coup in March 1982, Ershad made five official visits to China – November 1982, July 1985, July 1987, November 1988, and June 1990 throughout his presidency(Maniruzzaman, 1992). Ershad made a six-day official visit to China in November 1982. During that visit, China agreed to extend a loan of US\$12 million with soft credit (Hasan, 1981). China and Bangladesh signed the Joint Economic Commission (JEC) in November 1983, an important institutional framework for cooperation in economy, trade, science, and technology. The JEC also discussed issues related to the coordination of China-Bangladesh bilateral projects such as the proper implementation of projects and joint supervision over relevant protocols(MUSLIMS & Khan). The two countries granted each other "Most Favored Nation" (MFN) status in 1984, which began a new journey of enhancing bilateral trade relations. During the visit of Chinese President Li

Jiyanan to Dhaka in March 1986, China and Bangladesh upgraded their trade and economic cooperation and bilateral cooperation to a higher level. Li Jiyanan pledged an interest-free loan of US\$16 million for Bangladesh's economic development, (Xinhua, China, and South Asia, January-March, 1986). During Chinese Premier Li Peng's "goodwill visit" to Dhaka in November 1989, an agreement on trade and reciprocal visa exemptions between China and Bangladesh was also signed. Both sides signed the Visa Reciprocal Waiver Agreement and Trade Agreement (B.M. Jain, 2017). Hence the completion of the first China-Bangladesh Friendship Bridge near Dhaka in 1989 proved to be the biggest and most visible symbol of bilateral friendship between the two countries, (U.S. Department of State, "Bangladesh", July 27, 2020).

Bangladesh-China relations during Khaleda Zia's regime (1991-1996):

Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) leader Begum Khaleda Zia became Prime Minister of Bangladesh in March 1991. Begum Khaleda Zia made her first official goodwill visit to China on 18–20 June 1991 when bilateral cooperation focused on economic issues. is signed (S Ahmed - 2004). Khaleda Zia expressed her gratitude to China for assisting Bangladesh when the country endured a hurricane in 1991. China's leadership assured the development of friendly relations with Bangladesh and noted that bilateral relations are not affected by any international changes (CK Simon Wu - Asia Pacific Law Review, 2008). The seventh meeting of the China-Bangladesh Joint Commission was held in Beijing on August 27, 1992, during Khaleda Zia's tenure. Trade imbalance was one of the bilateral discussions that emphasized cooperative measures from both sides to reduce the growing trade imbalance (Pal, D. (2021).

Bangladesh-China relations during Sheikh Hasina's regime (1996-2001):

On 23 June 1996, Sheikh Hasina won the seventh parliamentary election and became the Prime Minister of Bangladesh for the first time. The Awami League government led by Sheikh Hasina has emphasized friendly relations with China. After assuming office as Prime Minister, Sheikh Hasina made her first foreign official visit to China in September 1996. During this visit, the Agreement on the Promotion and Protection of Investment, the Agreement on the Prevention of Double Taxation, and the Agreement on the Prevention of Tax Evasion were signed (Kemmer, D. M., Parikh, B., & Steigner, T. 2017).

Bangladesh-China relations during Khaleda Zia's regime (2001-2006):

In 2002, Begum Khaleda Zia made China-Bangladesh bilateral relations a landmark. The adoption of the "Look East Policy (Uddin & Bhuiyan, 2011)" by the then BNP-led four-party coalition government of Bangladesh opened up new avenues of cooperation. The then Premier of China Zhu Rongji paid an official visit to Dhaka in January 2002. Discussions between Prime Minister Zhu Rongji and Prime Minister Khaleda Zia discussed bilateral economic cooperation and increasing trade relations are given top priority. Some examples of agreements are economic and technical cooperation, the Certificate of Handover of the China-Bangladesh Friendship Conference Center, the Cultural Agreement Executive Program for 2001-2003, and four agreements signed between the two countries during the visit (Jansson, 2009).

Begum Khaleda Zia went on a four-day official visit to China from 23 to 27 December 2002. Chinese leaders called Bangladesh a "faithful and reliable friend" and attached high importance to the relationship between the two countries. The then-Chinese President Jiang Zemin reiterated the smooth progress of China-Bangladesh bilateral relations based on the Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence in a meeting with visiting Bangladeshi Prime Minister Khaleda Zia (Sarker, 2014). The two sides signed an exchange of letters of credit used for the project of the China-Bangladesh Friendship International Conference Center, conversion into grants, an agreement on economic and technical cooperation, and two other agreements (Uddin & Bhuiyan, 2011). According to the agreement, China announced USD 24 million as a grant instead of an interest-free loan to Bangladesh for the construction of an international convention center in Dhaka (Muni & Yong, 2013). China has agreed to grant over US\$7.26 million to Bangladesh for the construction of the Sixth China-Bangladesh Friendship Bridge over the Dhaleswari River in Munshiganj, Bangladesh (The Times of India, Dec 25, 2002). During Khaleda's visit, some initiatives were also taken to bridge the trade deficit on behalf of

China. Bangladesh requested duty-free access to 34 of its items in the Chinese market under the Bangkok Agreement due to its huge trade imbalance with China (Kazi Ihtesham and Mohammad M R, 2005).

In November 2003, China People's Political Consultative Conference Chairman Xia Qinglin visited Dhaka. The two countries signed the Agreement on the Executive Program of Economic and Technical Cooperation and Cultural Agreement for 2004-2006 (ECO, EPRC, PRB, 2007, op. cit.). Former Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao's visit to Dhaka on April 7-8, 2005 at the invitation of the then Bangladeshi Prime Minister Khaleda Zia strengthened China-Bangladesh bilateral relations. During the visit, five agreements, two memorandums of understanding, one agreement, and one exchange of letters were signed on trade, including five agreements to strengthen their trade relations. The agreement was signed (Bangladesh Army Weapon Systems Handbook Volume I, USA: International Business Publications, 2011). In addition, China has agreed to provide concessional loans for setting up digital telephone exchanges in metropolitan, important district headquarters and upazila growth centers in Bangladesh, as well as loans for Pagla Water Treatment Plant and North Dhaka (East) Sewage Treatment Plant and Associated Sewerage System (Joint Communique Between the Government of the People's China and Bangladesh", May 17, 2007). In November 2005 China expanded the Bangkok Agreement on Trade Arrangements within the Asia-Pacific Trade Agreement (APTA) with neighbors including Bangladesh to deepen trade cooperation (Mahmud Ali, Mingjiang Li, and Kalyan M. Kemburi, China's Power and Asian Security, 2015). Both countries declared 2005 as the "China-Bangladesh Friendship Year", marking the 30th anniversary of their diplomatic relations. A consensus was also reached on building a "comprehensive partnership of cooperation" for "long-term friendship" (Quazi Omar Foysal, 2014)(Prashant Kumar Singh, 2010).

Bangladesh-China relations during Fakhruddin Ahmed's regime (2006-2008):

Sino-Bangladesh economic relations also warmed during the tenure of Fakhruddin Ahmed, chief adviser to the then-caretaker government of Bangladesh from 2007 to 2009. Chinese Foreign Minister Yang Jiechi paid an official visit to Dhaka on 24–25 April 2008 and described Sino-Bangladesh relations as "good neighbors", "good friends" and "good partners". Yang Jiechi said, "It is one of China's efforts to continuously strengthen relations", and set policy", ("Bangladeshi Caretaker Government Chief Adviser Meets with Yang Jiechi", April 25, 2008). Xi Jinping pledged to continue Chinese support for Bangladesh's development and gave Bangladesh 600 crore taka (about US\$72 million) "free aid" and 50 lakh taka (about US\$60 thousand) "token gift" on the occasion of his visit. Fakhruddin Ahmed was welcomed by Chinese President Hu Jintao and Premier Wen Jiabao during his four-day official visit to China in September 2008 (Chowdhury, 2013). MoUs on economic and technical cooperation and Brahmaputra hydropower and agricultural technical cooperation were signed during the visit. During the official talks between Chinese Prime Minister Wen Jiabao and Fakhruddin Ahmed, China agreed to reduce the trade imbalance between the two countries and build Rooppur Nuclear Power Plant and North Way in Bangladesh. Stot Fertilizer has committed to accessing some Bangladeshi products in its market to help set up the company. Both sides reiterated the "win-win situation" for trade and investment (The Daily Star, September 17, 2008). In 2007, China-Bangladesh relations established bilateral trade worth US\$4.2 billion in economic cooperation (Harun ur Rashid, The Daily Star, September 23, 2008).

Bangladesh-China relations during Sheikh Hasina's regime (2009-2022):

After returning to power in January 2009, Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina maintained close contact with China for the third time on 12 January 2014 and the fourth time on 07 January 2019. A turning point in Sino-Bangladesh bilateral relations emerged when Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina paid an official visit to China from 17–21 March 2010 at the invitation of Wen Jiabao, Premier of the State Council of the People's Republic of China (M. Jashim Uddin, 2015). An agreement on economic and technical cooperation and a framework agreement on a concessional loan granted by China to Bangladesh and the construction of the seventh China-Bangladesh Friendship Bridge at Kazirtek was signed that year, ("China and Bangladesh", June 26, 2013). The then Chinese Foreign Ministry Qin Gang referred to Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina's visit as a "special contribution to the stable development of China-Bangladesh relations. And there is concern over Bangladesh's huge trade deficit with China, (Singh, 2010).

China-Bangladesh economic cooperation showed good momentum in 2010, the 35th anniversary of the establishment of diplomatic relations between the two countries. China has pledged its support to expand bilateral trade and provide preferential tariffs on more Bangladeshi products to reduce the huge trade deficit between the two countries. Because of these concerns, China allowed zero-tariff treatment for 4,762 Bangladeshi products in its market from 01 July 2010. China pledged to provide economic assistance to Bangladesh according to its capabilities to support Bangladesh's economic and social development ("China and Bangladesh", June 26, 2013).

China's then-Vice President Xi Jinping paid a two-day official visit to Dhaka in June 2010 at the invitation of Bangladeshi Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina. A four-point proposal—expanding economic cooperation, continuing frequent high-level exchanges, exploring areas for cooperation, and increasing cultural exchanges—is up for bilateral discussion. In addition, Xi Jinping reiterated China's willingness to expand bilateral trade, address trade imbalances, and encourage Chinese investment in Bangladesh,(China Daily, June 15, 2010).

Sheikh Hasina has publicly recognized China as an active partner and reiterated China's significance in the continued development of Bangladesh (B. M. Jain, 2017). Sheikh Hasina paid an official visit to China from June 6–11, 2014 at the invitation of Premier Li Keqiang to promote "closer and more extensive cooperation" between the two countries. "Partnership" was elevated. MoU-Agreement on Economic and Technical Cooperation, MoU on Establishment of Chinese Economic and Industrial Zone in Bangladesh and Joint Venture Agreement for Construction of Multi-Lane Road Tunnel Project under Karnaphuli River A 1320 MW Coal based in Kalapara Upazila, Patuakhali, Bangladesh Economic and trade relations were signed between the two countries regarding the establishment of ultra-supercritical power plants("Joint Statement between China and Bangladesh on Deepening the Closer Comprehensive Partnership of Cooperation", August 29, 2019). Sino-Bangladesh traditional relations reached a new height after Chinese President Xi Jinping's historic two-day visit to Bangladesh on October 14–15, 2016 (Establishing Strategic Partnership of Cooperation, October 14,2016). The visit was hailed as a "historic state visit" and a "new horizon" or "a new historic starting point" for China-Bangladesh bilateral relations. Although both sides have witnessed several state visits by senior officials in the 42 years of their diplomatic relations, the first state visit by a Chinese president to Bangladesh in the last 30 years marks a watershed in China-Bangladesh bilateral relations (The Star, November 15, 2016). The milestone visit of the Chinese President to Bangladesh has elevated China-Bangladesh bilateral relations to a higher level in trade, investment, energy and power, transport, information and communication technology, and agriculture (China Daily, October 15, 2016).

A landmark in China-Bangladesh economic relations was the signing of landmark agreements on investment and loans during Chinese President Xi Jinping's visit to Dhaka in 2016. As part of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the two countries have signed 27 agreements with Chinese financing, worth US\$24.45 billion, the largest single-country line of credit for Bangladesh to date (Ruma Paul,October 14, 2016). Among the 27 agreements, cooperation agreements on investment and production enhancement include 28 development projects to be linked with US\$ 21.5 billion in soft loans, economic and technical cooperation agreement for US\$ 80.3 million in grants, US\$ 700 million loan agreement for the construction of Karnaphuli tunnel, Dashekandi US\$280 million credit agreement for sewage treatment plant project. The memorandum of understanding signed between the two countries was a joint feasibility study on a free-trade area, new ICT framework, counter-terrorism cooperation, capacity building, and information sharing, addressing climate change risks, regional and international energy, and cooperation (Bangladesh, October 14, 2016).

Bangladesh formally joined the BRI in October 2016 during the visit of Chinese President Xi Jinping. China-Bangladesh economic cooperation has gained momentum under China's proposed One-Belt-One-Road or 'Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Bangladesh's official support of the BRI has added value to their relationship significantly. Both sides reached an agreement for the first time on achieving sustainable development and shared prosperity under the BRI(Lewis, Yang, Moise, & Roddy, 2021). The China-Bangladesh "Comprehensive Partnership of Cooperation" became the "Strategic Partnership of Cooperation" in 2016, marking a new chapter in China-Bangladesh bilateral relations ("Joint statement of the People's Republic of China and the People's Republic of Bangladesh", July 07, 2019). Agreed to upgrade from a

comprehensive partnership to a strategic partnership of cooperation. We agreed to enhance high-level exchanges and strategic contacts to advance our bilateral relations to a higher level (The Daily Star, "Chinese president for strategic partnership with Bangladesh", October 14, 2016). With the specific objective of exploring the possibility of enhancing cooperation in bilateral trade and investment, on 22 August 2016, the fourteenth session of the China-Bangladesh JEC was held in Dhaka in 2019. The JEC meeting reviewed bilateral trade and economic relations as well as the implementation of economic and trade arrangements (China-Bangladesh Joint Economic Commission 14th Session Held in Dhaka on 22 August 2016). Sheikh Hasina's Beijing from July 3-5, 2019 at the invitation of Chinese Premier Li Keqiang. China-Bangladesh strategic partnership deepened during the visit. The main agenda of Sheikh Hasina's three-day visit to Beijing was finance. Trade and Industry Issues (China-Bangladesh Joint Economic Commission, accessed on July 29, 2020). Chinese President Xi Jinping held bilateral talks on important issues with Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina at the Diaoyutai State Guesthouse in Beijing on 05 July 2019. President Xi Jinping emphasized the development of China-Bangladesh bilateral relations in various fields, including trade, investment, energy, transportation, telecommunications, infrastructure, and agriculture. Given the great potential of China-Bangladesh relations, Xi Jinping emphasized cooperation between the two countries in the digital economy and the Silk Road (Sun Haoran, Global Times, July 03, 2019).

Chinese Premier Li Keqiang also reiterated China's willingness to increase high-level exchanges, strengthen strategic mutual trust, enhance mutually beneficial cooperation, enhance people-to-people connections, and promote China-Bangladesh bilateral relations (Xinhua, "China, Bangladesh agree to Belt and Road cooperation", July 04, 2019). Along with these, China and Bangladesh have signed nine instruments, including five agreements, three memoranda of understanding, and one document. The five agreements include Framework Agreement on Power System Network Expansion and Strengthening under the Dhaka Power Distribution Company (DPDC) Area, Framework Agreement on Power Grid Network Strengthening Project, Agreement on Economic and Technical Cooperation between China and Bangladesh, Power System Network Expansion and Strengthening under DPDC Area Project. Government Concessional Loan Agreement for Strengthening and Buyer's Credit Loan Agreement for Expansion and Strengthening of Power System Network under DPDC Area Scheme (Rejaul Karim Byron, "China-funded Projects: Joint body to probe slow pace", The Daily Star, July 18, 2019). Around US\$1.76 billion in loan, agreements were signed for three projects during the visit (Silk Road Briefing, Jun 13, 2021). The two countries signed a memorandum of understanding on the establishment of the Investment Cooperation Working Group and the Yalu Zhangbo / Brahmaputra River and Hydropower Implementation Plan of Cultural Exchange and Tourism Program (BSS, "PM to return home from China tomorrow", July 05, 2019).

Bangladesh and China are fellow travelers in the journey of the new era:

On 1 October 2022, China celebrated the country's 73rd founding anniversary with a grand ceremony. Chinese embassies and Chinese communities in various countries also celebrate National Day. Officials of the governments of the respective countries and Chinese fans participated in all these events. World leaders including the President and Prime Minister of Bangladesh have sent congratulatory messages to Chinese leaders including Chinese President Xi Jinping on this occasion. Bangladesh celebrated China's National Day and 73rd founding anniversary a little early this time. On 24 September 2022, the Chinese Embassy organized a grand ceremony in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh, to mark the occasion (Mahmud Hashim, Dhaka Station, China International Radio, 2022/10/02). In the evening, the main event was preceded by the conference of the China-Bangladesh Enterprises Cooperation Forum and the Colorful Yunnan Exhibition. At the Bangabandhu Bangladesh-China Friendship Exhibition Center in Purbachle, Bangladesh Government Planning Minister MA Mannan, State Minister Dr. Shamsul Alam, State Minister for Culture KM Khalid, important people from Bangladesh and China, military-civil officials, politicians, diplomats of different countries, business leaders, journalists, researchers, teachers, and other private institutions were present. China's ambassador to Dhaka, Li Ziming, attended all three events and welcomed the guests and gave important speeches. In that event, the

officials of both countries recalled the traditionally friendly relations between Bangladesh and China. On this day, Bangladesh's national dailies published special circulars on the occasion of the 73rd founding anniversary of the People's Republic of China. The letter quoted parts of Bangladesh President Abdul Hamid and Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina's congratulatory messages to Chinese President Xi Jinping. Apart from this, a long article by the Chinese ambassador Li Ziming has been published - which reflects the traditional friendship between Bangladesh and China and the aspiration for a future joint journey on the path of development and prosperity. President Hamid's congratulatory message in *Crore Patra* said that Bangladesh and China enjoy bilateral relations based on mutual respect, common values, commonality of core national goals, and cooperation for mutual welfare. Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina said in the congratulatory message that Bangladesh and China enjoy excellent bilateral relations. The People's Republic of China is a valuable partner in our socioeconomic development. Our relationship has reached a new height in the last decade. Referring to Xi Jinping's visit to Bangladesh in 2016, the Prime Minister said, at that time we reached a consensus on expanding our bilateral relations into a strategic partnership. Recalling her visit to China in 2019 and meeting with President Xi Jinping there, Sheikh Hasina said that Bangladesh and China are working together on regional and global peace, security, stability, and development. In the article entitled 'Bangladesh's fellow traveler China in the joint campaign in the new era', the Chinese ambassador Li Ziming highlighted that China is moving forward intending to become a modern socialist country by 2049. Since the CPC met at the 18th National Congress in 2012, China has entered a new era on the road to Chinese socialism, with General Secretary Xi Jinping at the core of the party's leadership. Over the past decade, China has achieved rapid economic growth while maintaining long-term social stability. The country's GDP has grown at an average annual rate of 6.6 percent. China has brought about a historic solution to absolute poverty and thus has been able to build a moderately prosperous society in all areas. China is aware of and committed to its responsibility to the world. However, China firmly rejects any Cold War mentality, group conflict, or unilateral sanctions. Li Ximing also highlighted the Belt and Road Initiative-BRI to accelerate global development and the Chinese President's Global Security Initiative-GSI proposal and implementation initiatives to ensure global security. There is a deep connection between the Chinese dream of great national revival and the dream of a 'Golden Bengal'. Citing President Xi Jinping's speech, Ambassador Li Ziming said that he deeply believes that under the worthy leadership of the leaders of Bangladesh and China, the bond of friendship between the two countries will remain close and strong.

Bangladesh-China Relations at a new height:

Bangladesh Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina and Chinese President Xi Jinping termed their meeting as fruitful. Both the leaders feel that the agreement and memorandum of understanding have reached a new height in the relations between the two countries. President Xi Jinping and Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina said these things in a statement after the official meeting of the two leaders at the Prime Minister's office and the signing of 27 agreements and memorandums of understanding. President Xi Jinping said in his speech that China wants to take relations with Bangladesh to the stage of a long-term strategic partnership. Calling the friendship and partnership between the two countries wonderful, he said that 2017 is the year of exchange and friendship between the two countries. Addressing Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina, Xi Jinping said, 'I am very happy to visit a beautiful country like Bangladesh after six years. China and Bangladesh are good neighbors, good friends, and good partners. This visit will play a special role in the progress of the two countries as a whole. He said that agreements have been signed on various issues in the fruitful meeting with the Sheikh Hasina government. Xi Jinping said, "We have united to work together on maritime issues and counter-terrorism, jointly BCISM-FC, economic corridors and connectivity, and national and international issues and interests." The Chinese President also commented that China-Bangladesh relations will play a role in maintaining peace in the region. The Prime Minister said, "We have reached a consensus to work together in the business and investment, infrastructure, industry, power, energy, information, and communication technology, and agriculture sectors." He said, 'Today we witnessed the signing of 27 agreements and memorandum of understanding here. These agreements are related to trade, investment, marine economy, BCIM-EC, roads and bridges, railways, power, sea, ICT, industrial

production, capacity building, and skill development. Sheikh Hasina said, 'We have also inaugurated six projects (Prothom Alo, 14 October 2016, Bangladesh-China relations at a new height). He said, under this strategic partnership, we have agreed to work for the socio-economic development of the people of the two countries. Our efforts aim to become a knowledge-based middle-income country by 2021 and a developed country by 2041. Through this, Bangladesh will be free from hunger, poverty, and deprivation and will be able to build Bangabandhu's Golden Bangla.

Status of China-Bangladesh Relations:

In 1978, they had their first high-level visit, which marked the beginning of the improvement of bilateral relations. Bilateral trade relations gained greater momentum with the launch of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) in 2013. In 2016, Dhaka formally joined the BRI during the Chinese President's visit to Bangladesh, with the relationship elevated to a strategic partnership (Karim, R. and Liton, S. The Daily Star, 2016 "Strategic partners."). BRI membership has brought Bangladesh a total of US\$38.05 billion in Chinese investment, equivalent to nearly 10 percent of Bangladesh's gross domestic product, the largest financial contribution pledged to Bangladesh by any single country (The Daily Star, "Deals with China a turning point for Bangladesh,"). China is now Bangladesh's top bilateral trading partner, with 5 foreign direct investors, trade importers, and military hardware suppliers (The Financial Express, "BD-China trade to hit \$18b mark in two years," Accessed: January 22, 2022). In 2020, China granted Bangladesh duty-free access to its market for 97 percent of Bangladeshi products (Dhaka Tribune, "97% Bangladeshi products to get duty-free access to China," Accessed: January 22, 2022). Defense cooperation is the main framework of China-Bangladesh relations, China's economic advance is a relatively new phenomenon and it is growing, but defense cooperation is the main component of this bilateral relationship (Jiali, 2010). Since the late 1980s, the armed forces of the two countries have engaged in frequent high-level official visits and participated in joint training and exercises to strengthen cooperation. China has become Bangladesh's top exporter of military hardware. Bangladesh is China's second-largest arms export destination after Pakistan. During the period 2010–19, China accounted for 72 percent of Bangladesh's total arms imports (Bekkevold, 2020).

China-Bangladesh Relations in Geopolitics:

India has long been at the center of Bangladesh's geopolitics due to its geographical border proximity, cultural links, and above all its intervention as an ally against Pakistan during the Bangladesh Liberation War. The United States exerts the greatest economic and political influence over Bangladesh. China and Japan had a peripheral role until China's rise as an economic and military power until China began to influence its power. Bangladesh is embracing the new opportunities China represents. Driven primarily by economic incentives, China's massive investment in infrastructure development and other sectors has sealed its attraction. As Bangladesh-China bilateral relations deepen, India's concern is that Bangladesh may follow the likes of its traditional regional partners Nepal and Sri Lanka, which are hedging towards China. Bangladesh has avoided this trap by maintaining balanced relations with both China and India, emphasizing political and cultural affinity with India and economic ties with China (Anwar, 2019). The United States has exported US\$110 million worth of arms to Bangladesh since 2010, a pittance compared to the US\$2.59 billion Bangladesh spends on Chinese military equipment imports (ANAS A.Z.M. Nikkei Asia, 2020). In 2020, the United States took a proactive approach to military cooperation with Bangladesh, proposing a military modernization program beginning with Apache helicopters and missiles. There is a bilateral relationship of mutual interest with full respect for each other" (Riaz, 2022). The United States is Bangladesh's largest export country, accounting for 14.5 percent of total exports, primarily apparel, which is the country's main export and foreign exchange lifeline (Bangladesh (BGD) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners, 2020). Germany is the top exporter of Bangladesh's apparel trade, which accounted for USD 6.20 billion worth of goods in 2021, with Germany being Bangladesh's second largest export market overall, accounting for 14.2 percent of total exports (Comparative Statement on Export of RMG & Total Export of Bangladesh). China is in fierce competition between India and China. India displaced India as Bangladesh's trading partner in 2015, dropping from the position it had held for 40 years (Bangladesh (BGD) Exports, Imports, and Trade Partners, OEC,

<https://oec.world>). Imports from China accounted for 34 percent of Bangladesh's total imports in 2019, with China being Bangladesh's largest source of investment and a bilateral strategic partnership that India felt was lagging. India has deployed various strategic tools to counter China's trade (China's Engagement with Smaller South Asian Countries, 2019).

China's Economy and Neutrality Position:

Bangladeshi public perceptions of China are highly positive, with levels of enthusiasm varying between political, military, and business elites and ordinary citizens. A 2014 Pew Research survey found 77 percent of Bangladeshis view China positively, the highest positive rating of any country (Plagemann, 2022). Overall 43 percent of Bangladeshis prefer the United States as an ally. China owes its popularity to the perception that it is politically neutral and non-interventionist because it refrains from public comment on internal Bangladeshi issues (Faiz, 2022).

China sees a long-term strategic interest in strengthening relations with India's neighbors. Hence it provides low-cost sophisticated military hardware that Bangladesh could not get elsewhere. Chinese investment, trade, and exports are seeing gains as Chinese investment, trade, and exports ramp up in multiple sectors from physical to digital infrastructure. As Bangladesh In the world's fourth-largest Muslim-majority country, the predominantly positive view of the United States contrasts with prevailing perceptions of the Muslim world. Seventy-six percent of Bangladeshis viewed the United States favorably, the highest level in the subcontinent (China-Bangladesh Relations, 18 Aug 2022). In response to the Covid-19 pandemic, China has failed to deliver vaccines to Bangladesh despite its intense Covid diplomacy, while the US has prioritized Bangladesh. The US has donated 38.4 million vaccine doses, while China has provided only 5 million (China's Covid-19 vaccine tracker, Accessed: February 3, 2022). Anti-India sentiment reached its peak when the Indian firm Serum Institute failed to fully deliver on a pre-paid government order for the vaccine. Bangladesh had no choice but to buy the vaccine from China (DW 2021 "COVID,").

Future Prospects of China-Bangladesh Bilateral Trade Relations:

Bangladesh-China relations have strengthened considerably. Bangladesh faces the challenge of sheltering millions of Rohingya refugees. By prioritizing China's geopolitical and economic interests in Myanmar, Beijing has failed to pressure the Myanmar junta as Dhaka had hoped. If China maintains its current position on the Rohingya crisis with increasing implications for Bangladesh in the future, Dhaka's frustration may increase. This may damage China's friendly image in Bangladesh. The growing trade imbalance with China is a concern for Bangladesh. Although China gives duty-free access to 97 percent of Bangladesh's goods, it is unlikely that Bangladesh can reduce its trade gap with the world. Bangladeshi imports from China amounted to USD 17.75 billion in 2018, while Bangladeshi exports to China were only USD 985.41 million, resulting in a trade deficit ratio between Dhaka and Beijing of 1:17.3. has been (DCCI, Accessed in December 2021).

Figure 1: China Imports from Bangladesh

Source: China Customs, Tradingeconomics.com

Figure 2: China Exports to Bangladesh

Source: China Customs, Tradingeconomics.com

In the financial year 2021-22, Bangladesh imported goods worth 8 thousand 250 million dollars. Among them, only imports from China were worth 1,935 million dollars. In the fiscal year 2020-21, among the imports of 6,680 million dollars, 1,293 million dollars were from China, which is 21.30 percent of the total imports. In the last fiscal year 2020-2021, Bangladesh exported goods worth 680.65 million US dollars to China, and imported goods from China worth about 13 billion US dollars. China offers duty-free facilities on about 98 percent of its exports. Bangladesh is doing LDC graduation next year 2026. Bangladesh hopes that China will extend this trade facility for another three years till 2029. After LDC graduation, Bangladesh will sign trade agreements like FTA or PTA with various countries to get trade benefits. Bangladesh signed MoU with China. The possibility of forming a joint working group is being examined. Taking all aspects into consideration, there can be a trade agreement between Bangladesh and China (Bangladesh Time, June 08, 2022, GCG/SI). At present, the bilateral trade between China and Bangladesh is about 10 billion dollars. Bangladesh has a large trade deficit with China. Bangladesh exports only \$1 billion worth of goods against China's \$9 billion worth of imports. However, Chinese investment in Bangladesh is increasing every year. China's construction of dams on the Brahmaputra River is a cause of serious concern for Bangladesh as a downstream country, (The World Bank data: Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value-added).

EPB initiatives to reduce the trade deficit with China:

According to the statistics of Bangladesh Bank, the import value of Bangladeshi products was 996 million 44 million dollars. At this time, the value of the goods exported from Bangladesh to China was 326 million 85 thousand 620 dollars according to the data of the Export Development Bureau (EPB). China gave Bangladesh duty-free access to 98 percent of the goods under the tariff line. But despite this advantage, the export of Bangladesh is decreasing compared to before. On the other hand, 25 percent of Bangladesh's product imports in terms of value are from China. As a result, the size of the trade deficit between the two countries is also very large. The government of Bangladesh is concerned about the trade imbalance in this situation. The Export Promotion Bureau (EPB) under the Ministry of Commerce has started to determine the reasons for the decline in exports and what to do (EPB, May 15, 2022).

In the fiscal year 2019-20, Bangladesh imported goods worth 50 billion dollars from the world market. Among them, 11 billion dollars worth of products came from China. In contrast, during the same period, China imported goods worth 2400 billion dollars from all over the world whereas Bangladesh has been able to send only 600 million dollars worth of goods. That is Bangladesh imports about 20 percent of goods from China every year but exports less than 1 percent to China. Amid such a huge trade deficit between the two countries, China has provided duty-free facilities to 97 percent of Bangladeshi products under the tariff line since July 2020. Recently, the country's government has proposed to increase it to 98 percent by including leather and leather products. Even after getting this advantage, it will be very

difficult to take over the Chinese market, the commercial wing of Bangladesh in Beijing thinks. In this regard, a letter was also sent to the Ministry of Commerce of Bangladesh on behalf of Wing recently.

It is said by the commercial wing of the Bangladesh Embassy in China that the Chinese market is huge but competitive. At present, to increase the export in the Chinese market, there should be quality products and extensive promotion of products online. Bangladesh does not export any of the country's top 20 imports. Therefore, it is not possible to occupy the Chinese market with conventional products. The Commercial Wing of the Embassy has presented a review of the top 10 products exported from Bangladesh to the Chinese market in the last few years. Exports of all three of the five common commodities under review declined. On the other hand, exports of all five non-traditional products increased. Products such as traditional oven garments, knitwear, fish and crustaceans, and mollusks are gradually declining. In the financial year 2018-19, the export of woven garments to China was worth 28.25 million dollars, which decreased to 145.5 million dollars in the financial year 2020-21. And in the first six months of the fiscal year 2021-22, exports were worth 65.2 million dollars. In the financial year 2018-19, knitwear exports were worth 22.39 million dollars. In the last financial year, the export decreased to 12.57 million dollars. In the first six months of the current financial year, the exports were 4 crore 51 million dollars. Fish, crustacean, and mollusk products were exported to China in the fiscal year 2018-19 worth 7.39 million dollars. In the fiscal year 2020-21, exports decreased to 1 crore 42 million dollars. In the first six months of the current fiscal year, exports were worth \$1.7 million. The Commercial Wing says that 9.76 percent of China's imports in 2021 came from China-controlled Taiwan (EPB initiatives to reduce the trade deficit with China, May 15, 2022). Apart from this, China also imports products from Japan, South Korea, the USA, Australia, Brazil, Vietnam, Malaysia, Russia, Thailand, Indonesia, Chile, Italy, Canada, India, and South Africa. The demand for Bangladeshi products in the Chinese market is not very high. However, China Being a big market, Bangladesh has a demand for export products.

Conclusion:

Since the establishment of diplomatic relations in 1975, China-Bangladesh economic relations have remained strong and smooth under all successive governments of Bangladesh. All subsequent Bangladeshi governments have maintained good relations with the Chinese government and followed the policy of strengthening their friendship with China. Frequent high-level interactions have led to the formulation of many bilateral agreements on trade and economics and the expansion of economic relations as a result. China-Bangladesh economic relations have reached new heights in the 21st century with a wide range of cooperation and benefits. Bilateral economic relations between the two countries have become stronger and more active than before. Such intensive engagement and enhanced cooperation have longed for a cooperative strategic partnership between the two countries that is quite different from the earlier comprehensive partnership. Both countries are expected to further enhance their economic ties under the BRI facility.

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